

Ethics of reciprocity: A theoretical Investigation of Families' Moral Obligations and Expectation of care for Older Adults

Authors

Chika Rita Ikeorji

Faculty of Social Work, University of Calgary, Alberta, Canada

chika.ikeorji@ucalgary.ca (Corresponding author)

Orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7351-9725>

Chinonyerem Nwachukwu

Faculty of Social Work, University of Calgary, Alberta, Canada

chinonyerem.nwachukw@ucalgary.ca

Anyanwu, Uchechukwu Samuel, Ph.D

<https://orcid.org/0009-0009-4714-0514>

JR School of Business.

Northern Alberta Institute of Technology (NAIT)

usanyanwu@yahoo.co.uk

ABSTRACT

The ethics of reciprocity dictate that caregivers are expected to reciprocate the care they received and treat others as they would like to be treated. In Africa, caregiving expectations and obligations within families are built on familial relationships and there are moral principles that guide them. Applying these principles to caregivers can be challenging due to varying personal circumstances, resources, and capabilities. This study reflects on the ethics of reciprocity in the context of informal caregiving using the secondary method of data collection. It considers the cultural aspects of reciprocity in caregiving, particularly in African societies where caregiving is viewed as a moral obligation rooted in traditions and communal support. We found that caregivers' ability to provide care and support may differ based on factors such as employment status and skill sets; this disrupts the ethics of reciprocity. We recommend embracing a balanced approach to care and moving away from rigid expectations and obligations. Social workers can play significant roles in providing education and support to caregivers, promoting a shift in societal mindset regarding caregiving responsibilities.

Keywords: Ethics, Reciprocity, Informal Caregiving, Africa, Moral Obligation.

Introduction

The ethics of reciprocity is a context of familial informal caregiving that can be viewed as a crucial moral principle that directs the expectations and obligations of families towards one another when providing care (Lyons et al., 2002). Informal carers are people who offer unpaid support and care to family members, friends, or other people who require assistance with daily duties. According to McCarthy et al. (2013), the ethics of reciprocity holds that informal caregivers, particularly family members, are expected and under obligations to reciprocate the same care and good actions they received and treat others as they would like to be treated. Reciprocity is also believed to be a means of returning the love received by parents and not merely an act of repaying a debt such that care for older parents becomes motivated by gratitude (Laura, 2012). Commonly referred to as “the golden rule”, ethics of reciprocity could be related to how people would treat us in society. However, this can be challenging as the ethics of reciprocity cannot be used as a blanket expectation for all informal caregivers, particularly family members.

While caregivers need to provide care and support for their loved ones, the nature and extent of the care they can provide may vary based on their own personal circumstances, resources, and capabilities (Ikeorji & Ubani, 2024). For example, a family member who is also working a full-time job may not be able to provide the same level of care as someone who is unemployed and can devote more time to caregiving (Schulz, 2020). Similarly, a family member may not have the necessary skills or training to provide certain types of care, such as medical procedures, that a professional caregiver would be better equipped to handle (Given et al., 2008). Additionally, the ethics of reciprocity may not always be applicable in situations where the recipient of care is unable or unwilling to reciprocate. For instance, a person with dementia or a severe disability may not be able to reciprocate the care they receive in a meaningful way, and it would be unfair to hold their caregivers to a strict standard of reciprocity. This can be particularly challenging in the ethics of familial reciprocity of care. Thompson (2016) asserted that the idea of reciprocity is based on several cultural and religious traditions that uphold the idea that we should treat others how we would like to be treated. However, studies have argued differently highlighting that the idea of reciprocity is not necessarily based on a moral or ethical obligation to treat others how we would like to be treated, but rather on a pragmatic principle of social exchange (Sinunu et al., 2009). Studies have shown that understating moral obligations among family members improved compassion and effective care for older adults (Lyons et al., 2002; Satow, 2005).

Moral obligation in families, according to Stuifbergen and Van Delden (2011), is influenced by the degree of the older parent's need, the adult child's ability to provide care, and the parent-child connection. They also discussed that the duty to care is part of a broader range of filial obligations that may include companionship, financial support, and emotional support. Del-Pino-Casado et al. (2011) contended that the practice of reciprocity in caregiving is rooted in culture. According to cultural norms in Africa caring for the elderly is viewed as a duty that younger people must fulfill in return for the care they received when younger. Thus, if care is provided to loved ones there is a need to do the same in return which aside from being a moral obligation, is an expectation of the caregiving relationship (Lyons et al., 2002). However, the findings from the study of Satow (2005) hold a contrary view about caregiving and posit

that caregivers' approach to caregiving supersedes moral obligation. This suggests that caregivers may have various motivations and factors influencing their commitment and dedication to caregiving, which go beyond simply fulfilling a sense of duty or obligation. One possible interpretation of Satow's findings could be that caregivers are driven by personal relationships, empathy, or a genuine desire to provide support and care for their loved ones. This perspective emphasizes the emotional connection between caregivers and care recipients and suggests that their approach to caregiving is influenced by these deep-rooted bonds; providing care with empathy and compassion while putting aside personal feelings of resentment or contempt is a baseline for caregiving even when faced with challenging situations.

In African societies, reciprocity of caregiving is regarded as a tradition, which reflects a communal nature where there is an exchange of care services between families, friends, and neighbours such that caring for an older adult or a sick family member is considered a moral obligation expected of family members (Del-Pino-Casado et al., 2011). History has it that due to limited access to formal healthcare and social services in African communities, they rely on their family members and close acquaintances to take care of older adults by taking turns in providing care, reducing the burden of caregiving on one person or family alone (Uwakwe & Prince, 2004). Informal caregiving in Africa is a complex and multifaceted issue because it involves various ethical considerations that impact the caregiver, care recipient, family, and community. As noted by Leopold and Raab (2013), when a child follows the reciprocity standard, which is considered a norm for children and develops from a supportive parent-child relationship, it is generally perceived as paying back debts to parents that were accumulated earlier in life such that both parties benefit from the caregiving obligation. If there is a decline in the parent-child relationship reciprocity may not occur.

Cultural beliefs which serve as the basis for informal caregiving in Africa are experiencing changes and require new mechanisms of support and resources as well as a review of gender roles and policies of caregiving (Ikoerji & Warri, 2024). Therefore, this theoretical inquiry aims to answer these questions 1.) What are the ethics of reciprocity in informal caregiving? 2.) What is the understanding of the moral duties and expectations that families have for one another when providing care? 3.) What are the roles of social workers in informal caregiving? This research will not only add to the body of knowledge on informal caregiving ethics in Africa but also intends to provide insight into the other effective ways or mechanisms for families to support and care for their loved ones irrespective of the fact that informal caregiving has been the status quo for generations. This research is significant because it has the potential to improve caregiving policy and practice in Africa as well as the well-being and quality of life of care recipients and their families.

Theoretical framework

This review used the ethics of care theory as a framework. The ethics of care theory has been a significant philosophical framework in the late 20th century, largely shaped by feminist thinkers who sought to address the limitations of traditional ethical theories focused predominantly on abstract principles like justice and rights (Held, 2020). Carol Gilligan as pioneer of the theory, challenged the male-centric focus

Received: 12 November 2024

Revised: 4 December 2024

Accepted: 18 November 2024

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113

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.14515779](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14515779)

of existing moral theories by highlighting how women's moral reasoning often emphasizes care, empathy, and relational dynamics rather than strict adherence to abstract principles (Gilligan, 2011). Further building on Gilligan's insights, Nel Noddings further developed the theory in her seminal book, "Caring: A Feminine Approach to Ethics and Moral Education" (1984), emphasizing the central role of caring relationships in moral reasoning (Branicki, 2020). The core assumptions of the Ethics of Care Theory are that moral values are grounded in the context of personal relationships and that ethical behavior arises from our responsibilities to care for others (Gilligan, 2011). This theory argues that caregiving and the maintenance of relationships are fundamental to understanding and practicing morality.

The Ethics of Care Theory suits this study on families' moral obligations and expectations of care for older adults because it directly addresses the relational nature of caregiving. Unlike theories that focus solely on individual autonomy or abstract principles of justice, the Ethics of Care Theory provides an exact framework for understanding how familial relationships shape moral responsibilities. It allows for a detailed examination of how family members perceive their obligations to care for older adults based on empathy, mutual support, and the context of their relationships (Held, 2020). This theoretical perspective is valuable for exploring how familial care is not just a duty but also an expression of deep relational bonds and emotional connections (Satow, 2005). With focus on the relational aspects of caregiving, the Ethics of Care Theory shows the ways in which family dynamics influence caregiving expectations and practices, making it a viable tool for understanding the ethical dimensions of care within familial contexts.

This theory also provides a lens for understanding and addressing the complexities of family caregiving which is common in most families as it pertains to social workers and researchers on informal care. It emphasizes the importance of recognizing and supporting the relational dynamics that underpin caregiving responsibilities, which can lead to more empathetic and effective interventions (Gilligan, 2011). By acknowledging the central role of care relationships, social workers can better engage with families, facilitate more supportive care arrangements, and address the emotional and relational aspects of caregiving (Ikeorji & Warri, 2024). For future researchers, the Ethics of Care Theory offers a framework to explore how caregiving practices and moral obligations vary across different familial and cultural contexts. It can guide research into the ways that care relationships influence caregiving expectations and outcomes, contributing to a deeper understanding of family dynamics and the development of more nuanced policies and practices in elder care (Okoye, 2014). Thus, this theory provides a framework for research and practice in that it helps promote a more comprehensive approach to understanding and supporting family caregiving with emphasis on the relational and emotional dimensions that are central to effective care.

Materials and Method

This study used a secondary method of data collection. It is a reflection on an independent course by the first author. Relevant materials and articles from 2013 to 2023 were sourced from Google Scholar. Terms such as 'reciprocity', 'ethics of care', 'caregiving in Africa', and 'care obligations' were used to obtain

relevant articles that covered the topic. During the search and as a means of inclusion criteria, we included articles that had similar ideas, published in English and peer-reviewed and qualitative studies. Out of the 603 academic and grey literature found, we excluded articles that did not resonate with the central aim and key concepts for the review (Dehalwar & Sharma, 2023). We went further to look out for studies with an African context since our topic is centered on the ethics of caregiving in Africa and finally settled for 48 studies including world reports, quarterly reviews, and books.

Results

Conceptualizing ethics of reciprocity

The ethics of reciprocity is hinged on the principle of mutual respect, fairness, and moral obligation in human relationships. This concept emphasizes the importance of reciprocal responsibilities, where individuals are expected to treat others with the same level of care, dignity, and consideration that they would expect in return (Laura, 2012). It is grounded in the moral belief that equitable and respectful treatment should guide interpersonal interactions, fostering an environment of shared responsibility. In informal caregiving, the ethics of reciprocity shifts the focus from caregiving being a one-way process to a mutual exchange between the caregiver and the care recipient (Okoye, 2014). While it is often assumed that caregivers solely provide support and care, reciprocity suggests that care recipients, too, hold a certain level of responsibility in this relationship, even if it is not always material or physical. Care recipients can offer emotional validation, recognition of the caregiver's efforts, or foster a relational bond that benefits both parties (Pype, 2013). This reciprocal relationship ensures that the dignity, autonomy, and well-being of both individuals are honored, reducing the risk of caregiver burnout and enhancing the quality of care provided.

Similarly, the ethics of reciprocity in informal caregiving challenges traditional hierarchical models of care where one party is always in the position of providing, and the other is consistently receiving. Instead, it introduces a model where both parties are contributors to the caregiving process in ways that align with their capabilities, whether through emotional support, acknowledgment, or active participation (Held, 2020). This balance of roles helps to preserve the dignity and well-being of care recipients, while also reinforcing the moral duty of caregivers to provide care that is not only transactional but empathetic and respectful. Reciprocity in care reflects broader social and moral frameworks where care relationships are viewed as part of a social contract (Lyons et al., 2002). In many cultural contexts, including in African settings, there are moral expectations that caregiving should be based on communal values of solidarity, ubuntu, and shared responsibility (Twum-Danso, 2022). These principles resonate deeply with the ethics of reciprocity, as they highlight the collective nature of caregiving, where families and communities share responsibilities and ensure that both caregivers and care recipients are supported. This contrasts with individualistic models where care responsibilities fall solely on one person, often leading to inequitable burdens.

Historical background of reciprocity in informal caregiving

In Africa, informal caring is very common and is a deeply ingrained cultural practice (Uwakwe & Prince, 2004). This strategy enables older individuals in Africa to rarely seek hospital-based care. According to the study by Osundina et al. (2016), informal caregiving is successful in Africa because of the traditional African society's (horizontal and vertical) network of kinship, family, and household units that cater to the needs of elderly people. This refers to the interconnected system of familial relationships and social connections within African societies such that "horizontal" is the relationships among individuals who belong to the same generation or age group within the kinship network (the connections between siblings, cousins, and other relatives who share a similar status in terms of age and generation) while "vertical" pertains to the hierarchical relationships within the kinship system, typically between older and younger generations (relationships between parents and children, grandparents and grandchildren, and other hierarchical connections that involve differences in age and authority). Twum-Danso (2022) argued that the role of reciprocity has been carried by women more than men and the narrative has remained unchanged even in contemporary times as male children migrate to other places. Uwakwe et al. (2009) estimated that children of the elderly makeup most caregivers, nearly 80% of them are female.

Care exchanges between older people and their younger family members are motivated by a sense of need to repay a benefit, known as reciprocity (Ugargol & Bailey, 2020). Furthermore, Schulz and Eden (2016) opined that complex family arrangements and non-traditional households are much more prevalent today than in the past. The impact of this change on family caregiving is significant since adult children may feel less obligated to look after their parents and stepparents. Contemporary times have witnessed the migration of people, changing the place and practice of reciprocity in informal caregiving. These factors have caused a dynamic change in care provision because people now consider whose responsibility it is to provide care and the type of care they expect to receive in return (Ikeorji & Warri, 2024). However, informal caregiving keeps increasing as compared to former years when it was still uncommon (Broese van Groenou & De Boer, 2016; World Health Organization, 2020). Giving care to elders and other vulnerable community members was regarded as an honor and a means to demonstrate respect and affection in many African societies where people in need received care and support from family members and close friends, including aid with daily living activities, transportation, and emotional support (Okoye, 2014). It was generally believed that no one should be left alone as everyone worked together to support each other to avoid shame, neglect, and abandonment and children were always seen as children to everyone such that relatives could go and live with other family members just to help in caregiving.

In Sub-Saharan Africa, the family is regarded as the approved institution for the provision of long-term care for older adults (Aboderin & Hoffman, 2012). This sole responsibility of the family often results in caregiver burden and care deficiencies due to the complex needs of the aging population. According to Shih (2020), over the last five years, the prevalence of providing care for a family member or friend who is 50 years of age or older has increased from 18.2% to over 21.3%. From this, we can infer that there is a need for a caregiver in almost every home. In Congo, older individuals with large families are frequently moved from one home to another. Typically, the older individual is taken care of by their offspring,

whereas those who have numerous dependents generally do not face difficulties in meeting their caregiving responsibilities (Pype, 2013). Most older adults have specific children or grandchildren they prefer to stay with, and it is very common for women to serve as grandmothers to care for and nurture younger adults (Pype, 2013). In Tanzania, because of demographic shifts, reciprocity and the performance of care is progressively giving way to the acceptance of the professionalization of care, which opens the door for various non-kin support groups; ethnic-related, religious, state, and non-governmental organization to provide care for older people (Van der Geest, 1997). Also, due to a lack of or ineffective health policies to address the needs of older individuals, Africa is experiencing an increase in the number of elderly people who are vulnerable populations with poor health (WHO, 2011).

Furthermore, Pharr et al. (2014) stated that in some parts of Africa, it has also been demonstrated that the role of caring, namely who is responsible to provide care, is influenced by a culture's orientation toward either individualism or collectivism and the degree to which the values of these orientations are embodied. Saying no to someone is interpreted as abandonment and rejection in some cultures, especially those with a collectivistic attitude where the duty of caregiving is culturally mandated based on a defined hierarchy of "who" is expected to care. Markus and Kitayama (1991) opined that the family and community were highly valued in traditional African communities, and providing care was viewed as the duty and responsibility of family members and close friends. Tanyi et al. (2018) affirm that the African family system operates in a way that children in their respective families are saddled with the responsibility of ensuring that their older parents were properly taken care of and lacked nothing to enable them to have a good old age experience. This means that care in old age is guaranteed if older adults had children who would take up such responsibilities as an obligation for the care received by their parents.

Roles of ethics of reciprocity in informal caregiving

In redefining caregiving as a mutual relationship rather than a one-sided obligation, the ethics of reciprocity play an important role. In many informal caregiving settings, caregivers are often viewed as providers of care, while care recipients are seen as passive recipients; the ethics of reciprocity challenges this assumption by promoting a model of caregiving that emphasizes mutual contribution (Pype, 2013). While care recipients may depend on caregivers for physical or emotional support, they can reciprocate in other ways, such as providing emotional validation, gratitude, or fostering a sense of purpose for the caregiver (Okoye, 2014). For example, a family member caring for an older parent may find that the parent offers emotional comfort or wisdom, which in turn strengthens the caregiver's resolve and emotional well-being. This reciprocity fosters a more balanced relationship that recognizes both the care recipient and caregiver's roles in the caregiving process.

The ethics of reciprocity enhances the quality of care provided in informal caregiving settings by fostering respect and understanding between caregivers and care recipients (Ugargol & Bailey, 2020). When caregiving is rooted in reciprocity, caregivers are more likely to approach their role with empathy and respect for the care recipient's autonomy and preferences (Satow, 2005). We see this in a situation where

Received: 12 November 2024

Revised: 4 December 2024

Accepted: 18 November 2024

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117

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.14515779](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14515779)

a caregiver who recognizes the reciprocal nature of the relationship may involve the care recipient in decision-making processes, even if the recipient has physical limitations. This could involve asking the care recipient how they would prefer their daily routine to be structured or respecting their cultural or personal preferences regarding health care. This makes caregiving processes become more person-centered, improving the care recipient's overall well-being and satisfaction.

Aside from ensuring that care recipients benefit from quality care provided, the ethics of reciprocity also plays a critical role in preventing caregiver burnout. Informal caregiving is often a physically and emotionally demanding task, particularly when the caregiver is responsible for the long-term care of a dependent individual (Broese et al., 2016). The ethics of reciprocity ensures that caregivers receive emotional support and recognition for their efforts, which can mitigate the feelings of exhaustion, isolation, and frustration that often accompany caregiving (Satow, 2005). The reciprocal element in providing care ensures that the caregiving experience is not burdensome, nor leading to resentment or a decline in the quality of care provided. In some multigenerational households, common in African and other communal societies, the role of reciprocity plays out in situations where the younger generation provides physical care and the older adults often play a critical role in maintaining family values, offering moral guidance, and sharing cultural wisdom (London, 2014). This shows mutual exchange of caregiving that is respectful and balanced, rather than hierarchical.

Addressing power dynamics within caregiving is also a role of ethics of reciprocity. In cases where a caregiver holds significant control over the care recipient's daily life and decisions, reciprocity promotes a more equitable relationship by emphasizing the moral obligation to respect the care recipient's rights and dignity (Ikeorji & Warri, 2024). Sometimes, caregivers may want to assume full control of older adult's activities especially those with cognitive impairments, such as dementia. But the ethics of reciprocity encourage caregivers to seek the care recipient's input and preferences as much as possible, ensuring that their autonomy is not unnecessarily undermined (Miller, 2016). This approach aligns caregiving with ethical principles of fairness and justice, even in challenging circumstances and promotes healthy, equitable, and sustainable caregiving practices in informal settings.

Moral obligations and expectations of families

In most households, children receive care and necessities in exchange for helping with chores including sweeping, cooking, cleaning, watching after younger siblings, and helping with parental duties to temporarily lessen the strain on their caregivers. The motivation behind these reciprocal obligations in intergenerational relationships stems from the understanding that both the carer and care recipients are dependent on one another and have obligations to one another, characterized by reciprocities of duty and interdependence (Afua, 2022). Studies have shown that caregivers provide different forms of support for older adults. Support for older adults is provided based on the older adult's most felt needs. According to Akinrolie et al. (2020) older adults in Nigeria receive support through financial support, caregiving, and emotional support from their children. In informal care, reciprocity is viewed in such a way that care can

be either with the expectation of fair treatment when paying back or negative with no expectation of return or fair treatment (Sahlins, 1972). Ugargol and Bailey (2021) discovered that reciprocity is perceived as a duty, cultural norm, historical obligation of care, and spousal responsibility that is typically internalized, and when children fail to reciprocate, it results in irritation and the possibility of not getting care, but in some instances, if reciprocity occurs, it leads to the intergenerational transfer of money and assets.

Findings from the study of Tsai and Dzorgbo (2012) revealed that when older adults receive more help from their adult children their subjective well-being is better due to the bond and familial relationships between them. Bouchard et al (2010) asserted that the best help, care, and support is that which is received from a family member. The study posits that the best form of care is that provided by a family member. This may be the reason Africans do not aspire to formal care. However, this may not be the same in every home and could be based on the level of relationship that exists between the parents and the children. Stuifbergen and Delden (2011) also noted that certain conditions are needed that would elicit if there would be moral obligations and expectations of care to provide for aging parents, which include the degree of the parent's need, the adult child's ability to provide care, and the relationship between the parent and child. They viewed the duty to provide care as a part of a broader range of filial obligations that may include providing companionship, financial support, and emotional support when the need arises. Moral obligations can also be viewed as a social exchange, as Schulz (2016) asserts that in the context of providing family care, the caregiver may offer many types of assistance, such as emotional support, physical care, and financial support, in exchange for gratitude, recognition, and the satisfaction of carrying out their responsibility as a family member. In this way, the caregiver can expect to receive support and consideration from the care recipient or other family members in the future, creating a sense of reciprocity. According to Lyons et al. (2002), the reciprocity of the relationship and the interdependence of the two people who are involved in caregiving can be both a fulfilling and stressful experience for both parties depending on the effectiveness of coping mechanisms like social support, adjusting to changing circumstances, and finding meaning in caregiving. People who have a strong personal relationship with care recipients find caregiving a rewarding experience and render service as expected.

Even though reciprocity is seen as a moral obligation with care expectations, there are consequences if they are not met. Afua (2022) stated that children may be physically punished or lose care because of failing to uphold these reciprocal obligations, while older persons may experience disdain, disobedience, or neglect when it comes to household responsibilities. Children may be deprived of their inheritance if they do not meet their parent's expectations of care which according to Akinrolie et al. (2020) is a form of intergenerational support. So, most children provide care with an expectation of a parting gift from their parents. Satow (2005) frowns at this act because it makes children render help of compulsion and the expectation to get an inheritance instead of providing care as it is required of them as children. With the changing demographics due to migration and urbanization, informal caregiving patterns, expectations, and obligations should be reconsidered.

Ethics of reciprocity in informal caregiving

Reciprocity can contribute to the development of a more harmonious and equal caregiver relationship if the ethics of reciprocity are kept (Miller, 2016). To be reciprocal, the care recipient must show their gratitude and appreciation for the assistance given, work cooperatively with the caregiver, and offer emotional and social support where necessary. According to Ivanoff and Oden (2013), caregivers and public health nurses must be aware of human rights like equality and nondiscrimination since they include ethics, morality, and justice in their work which is said to have a strong foundation in ethics and social justice. Thompson (2016) professed that social workers should be dedicated to critically reflective practice, challenge bureaucratization trends and risk-averse cultural norms, and search for innovative ways to promote reciprocity, such as acknowledging the dynamic nature of social life, looking beyond the surface of a situation, challenging societal presumptions, and reiterating the notion that dependency does not preclude reciprocity. This means that social workers can acknowledge the dynamic nature of social life by recognizing that circumstances and relationships evolve. They can look beyond the surface of a situation by delving deeper into the underlying factors and complexities that contribute to individuals' experiences and by challenging societal presumptions, social workers can question, and challenge commonly held beliefs or stereotypes that may hinder understanding and perpetuate inequality. This will help to understand that individuals in vulnerable positions still can contribute, provide support, and engage in reciprocal relationships which promotes a more inclusive and empowering approach that recognizes the inherent dignity and agency of all individuals, regardless of their perceived level of dependency. Similarly, Laura (2012) affirms that when it comes to providing care for one another, families have a variety of moral obligations which include the duty to aid and support to family members who are in need, to respect the autonomy and dignity of the care recipient, and to make sure that the care is of a high standard and satisfies their needs. Thus, for families to care for their loved ones effectively and compassionately, they must understand these moral commitments.

Moreover, the WHO Global Strategy and Action Plan on Ageing and Health (2018) emphasized the significance of families as the main providers of care for older individuals across all societies. Family members bear a moral duty to offer assistance and caregiving, yet the caregiver's responsibility to provide care must be balanced with the need to uphold the care recipient's autonomy and dignity during the caregiving process. This obligation to respect ethical considerations encompasses various aspects of care and support. One may assume that it is the benefits of informal caregiving that propel the idea of reciprocity and expectations from parents. Wiles et al. (2012) noted that many older adults opt to age in place rather than move into assisted living or nursing facilities because of the feelings of security and familiarity with their homes and communities, as well as a sense of attachment or connection. All these helps them develop their sense of self through their level of independence, autonomy, and caring interactions. There is therefore a need for informal caregivers to provide support and assistance with daily living activities, transportation, and medication administration. Informal caregiving is important to older adults as it improves their quality of life as explained by Malhotra et al. (2012) that informal caregivers frequently give care recipients emotional support, a listening ear, and company which can enhance their mental health and general well-being. More so, the preference for informal caregiving by older adults

Received: 12 November 2024

Revised: 4 December 2024

Accepted: 18 November 2024

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120

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.14515779](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14515779)

could be related to reducing medical expenditures because the support they receive prevents unnecessary emergencies and hospitalizations due to close monitoring and early intervention (Houtven & Norton, 2004).

The carer and the care recipient can benefit from informal caregiving when it is properly coordinated. However, it can also be difficult, time-consuming, and emotionally draining (McCarthy et al, 2013). The study conducted by Broese et al. (2016) revealed that difficulties in informal caregiving such as people's inability to provide care and the decline in the number of caregivers arise due to changing cultural patterns, population aging, and rising female labor giving rise to an increase in the need for informal caregiving. These changes and complex needs would continue to increase as the aging population increases (WHO, 2018), and this increase is expected to double by the year 2050. Moreso, Laura (2012) posits that challenges occur in informal caregiving due to conflicts over autonomy, and the effects of caregiving on personal relationships and job aspirations which disrupt mutual relationships in the caregiving practice. Furthermore, a strain on the physical and mental health of caregivers and care recipients which include their financial position and social isolation according to Lyons, (2002) is seen as part of the challenges of informal caregiving. Thus, as part of some coping strategies, caregivers should adjust based on the changing circumstances and find meaning in caregiving. Del-Pino-Casado et al. (2011) propose creating other cultural motivations which could serve as successful interventions to support informal carers.

Discussion

Balancing obligations and expectations of care

Even though some communities still try to uphold the tradition, which is a part of African heritage and culture, the recent rapid changes afflicting African societies because of urbanization and globalization are bringing about a paradigm shift in the practice of reciprocity of caregiving in informal care. This means that the African traditional family structure and family roles are experiencing rapid change and there is a need to make an adjustment and balance care patterns. One important aspect of change according to Szinovacz and Davey (2007) is the caregiver network and care responsibilities which include understanding children's ability to provide care for their older parents. These children have demands, commitments, and resources that change over time because of political and social structures. Therefore, family support systems must be seen dynamically, considering how these members' circumstances are changing which could make them not reciprocate care as expected or meet up with family obligations. Cultural expectations of females as sole caregivers should be reconsidered as opined by Kim and Woo (2022) that more daughters are entering the workforce, and there is a high infertility rate resulting in smaller families and living far away due to marriage are factors influencing care. These factors may affect care roles and responsibilities for other family members and fall onto those who may not be competent due to an over-reliance on female children.

Likewise, when caregivers feel burdened by obligations and expectations, the provision of care may be devoid of empathy and conducted less professionally. According to Li (2004), it is time to reevaluate the roles and expectations of caregivers because the absence of formal care, such as professional home carers, privately compensated caregivers, and volunteers, leads to inadequate care services, particularly in the areas of personal care and special care (complex situations) because of a lack of formal training and inadequate skills. In agreement with this, Broese and Boer (2016) note that the absence of professional home caregivers in informal caregiving is due to the government's and the healthcare industry's lack of support, as well as a lack of basic resources like clean water and medical equipment. As a result, older adults suffer from poorer health outcomes because caregivers do not ask for assistance from the government or others. If adequate and accessible healthcare services for older adults from formal care settings would improve the quality of health of older adults, cultural structures and perceptions of care need to be challenged. Perhaps older adults may embrace formal care if we critically examine and challenge the cultural norms, beliefs, and attitudes that shape the way care is understood and provided. This will help to address underlying biases, stereotypes, and ageist attitudes that may hinder older adults from appreciating formal care. More so, Satow (2005) opined that the right thing to do is to take care of older parents even if they did not provide care to their children and not base it on expectations and reciprocity but out of human empathy. We should care for people because we want to and not be borne out of compulsion. This means that caregiving should be approached by providing care with love and compassion and setting aside any personal feelings of resentment or disdain even when doing so is difficult.

In addition to the above-mentioned assertions, Ugargol and Bailey (2021) posit that the best way to prevent frustration and depression in old age which emanates due to the social shift brought on by migration and urbanization is that reciprocity expectations from children be scaled back. In affirmation that there is a need to balance expectations of care which when neglected, Twum-Danso (2022) states that children may lose access to care and face physical punishment, while older persons may be mistreated, ignored, or disregarded in their responsibilities as family members. These may leave more fear, anxiety, and the quest for children to engage in the unhealthy acquisition of wealth just to make sure they have the financial resources required to meet up with expectations of taking good care of their parents in exchange for the care they have received in the past. There is a need to embrace the new trend of change in society so that adult children will not be overburdened by care expectations and obligations but restructure their lives to adjust to new roles. This is because, in today's rapidly changing society, it is crucial for us to acknowledge the need for embracing new trends, restructure our lives, adjust, and adapt to the evolving dynamics of care expectations and obligations with special concerns of adult children being overburdened with caregiving responsibilities.

Recent societal trends and shifts have paved the way for alternative approaches to caregiving, emphasizing the importance of shared responsibility, professional assistance, and community support. If adult children embrace these new trends it could help to avoid being overwhelmed by the expectations and obligations

placed upon them. They can focus on creating a more balanced life that encompasses their own personal and professional aspirations through proactive discussions about expectations, boundaries, and available support systems while still being supportive of their aging parents. Additionally, society should encourage a shift in mindset by recognizing and valuing the diverse contributions individuals can make in caregiving roles. This means moving away from the notion that caregiving is solely the responsibility of immediate family members and acknowledging the importance of professional caregivers and community resources. By recognizing and appreciating the efforts of all individuals involved in the care of aging parents, we can foster a more inclusive and supportive environment for everyone.

Within the cultural expectations and obligation of care, we need to understand that expectations sometimes are not always realistic and desirable. In as much as older parents cared for their children, it is not all parents who provided care, and having established that reciprocity comes with maintaining a good relationship with carers, children will not be willing to provide care and support to parents who did not care for them especially providing a good nurturing environment because some parents are abusive and often neglect their children. Adult children also have a responsibility to their immediate family and job and may not have the opportunity to be caregivers to their parents, hence the need for considering formal care because children will not always be available to provide care and support when needed. If children are expected to take care of their old parents, it can promote unequal power dynamics and maintain a culture of obligation and guilt instead parents who can support themselves should not rely on their children for care, and children should not be made to feel bad for putting their own needs and wellbeing first (König et al., 2019). Thus, the bond between parents and kids should not be viewed as only an exchange of care on a transactional basis. Instead, it ought to be founded on adoration, support, and respect for one another, as corroborated in the study of Satow (2005), that care for parents should resonate from an act of empathy and humility. Although it shouldn't come at the expense of their well-being, children should be encouraged to keep up good relationships with their parents.

Balancing expectations in informal caregiving is very important for the well-being of both caregivers and care recipients in Africa. Respecting both the autonomy of the individual receiving care and the autonomy of the caregivers is crucial. We must understand that everyone has the right to make their own choices and establish their limits. Informal carers should not be expected to handle all caring duties alone; instead, they can look for outside assistance, such as respite care, home health aides, or support groups. In informal care, there should be a clear strategy in place for who will be responsible for what duties and when, and the plan should be flexible and adaptive as needs change over time. Given that everyone has various unique capabilities and limitations, caregiving responsibilities should be appropriately distributed among family members in such a way that guarantees equitable, long-lasting caregiving with reasonable expectations.

From this reflection, we see the necessity for families to embrace the new trend of change in society regarding caregiving expectations and obligations. By restructuring lives and adjusting to new roles, adult

children can avoid becoming overburdened and find a healthier balance between personal aspirations and caregiving responsibilities. This requires open communication, shared responsibility, and a shift in societal mindset to recognize and support the diverse contributions of caregivers. Ultimately, by embracing these changes, we can create a more compassionate and sustainable care system for the benefit of both adult children and aging parents. Some scholars (Ikeorji & Warri, 2024; Okoye, 2014; Tsai & Dzorgbo, 2012) state that embracing familial relationships, and the well-being of parents is important for positive progress in informal caregiving. These will help to reduce stress, burnout, and lack of support experienced by caregivers and increase the support and well-being of carers, care recipients, families, and communities.

Implications for social work practice and family caregiving

Social work as one of the care professions provides a platform for social workers to serve individuals with equity and justice. The National Association of Social Workers (2014) conveyed that the primary goal of the social work profession is to improve people's well-being and assist in meeting their basic needs, paying special attention to the needs and empowerment of those who are weak, oppressed, and living in poverty, with an emphasis on the individual's well-being and that of the society. Environmental factors that influence and cause social problems with daily living are an aspect social work pays close attention to because most problems people are challenged with emanate from their social environment (NASW, 2014). According to Biegel et al. (1991), one of the many functions of social workers in informal caregiving is to assist family caregivers, who encounter many difficulties and need it. Social workers inform carers about the health state of the care receiver, support them in managing symptoms, and help them come up with good coping mechanisms. These approaches also help caregivers in dealing with situations that affect their health and in making decisions for clients.

Similarly, the need for sharing knowledge helps families who are unprepared when a crisis occurs. It helps relieve the shock of younger adults' experience who might not know the right support to provide to their grandparents and prepares them ahead of any future challenges. As educators and advocates, social workers serve as bridges to the available resources in the community for families, especially for families who might lack adequate understanding of the resources available both inside and outside their community (Lombard & Twikirize, 2014). Social workers lessen their load by recommending and promoting local services like long-term care facilities, adult day care facilities, alternative living arrangements, and other home health care (London, 2014). There can never be enough emphasis placed on the value of support and communication between carers and care recipients. Social workers play a crucial role in assisting families in navigating the difficult emotional and logistical challenges of caring and in supporting the well-being of both caregivers and care recipients. Through communication, social workers set clear expectations and boundaries around caregiving (Schulz & Eden, 2016). More so, the ethics of reciprocity can be enhanced and advanced by social workers in supporting policies and programs that assist caregivers, such as respite care and support groups thereby ensuring that caregivers have the tools and assistance they need to deliver evidence-based practice. This is affirmed by the study of Broese and De

Boer (2016) which proposes the necessity of enacting legislation to support caregivers and promote a more equitable division of care responsibilities, as well as the potential benefits and drawbacks of informal caregiving for both caregivers and care recipients.

Geriatric social workers need to ensure that older adults' needs are met by incorporating holistic care plans to address the social, physical, emotional, and financial needs of older adults which often leads to challenges in their well-being and quality of life. According to Hajek and Behrens (2019), due to the complex health and social concerns that older persons frequently deal with as well as the growing need for geriatric care for the aging population, a collaborative and interdisciplinary approach to geriatric care is necessary. The need to address social determinants of health globally will contribute to the reduction of poverty and isolation, two factors that can significantly affect the health outcomes of older persons. Social workers can contribute to geriatric care in a variety of settings, including hospitals, long-term care facilities, and community-based organizations as well as coordinate professional development plans for geriatric care to gain a thorough understanding of the needs and challenges of older adults as well as knowledge of the most recent research (Getz, 2010).

Conclusion

This paper explored the ethics of reciprocity in informal caregiving and sought to understand the moral duties and expectations of families when they provide care for older adults. It was established that there are different ethical norms required for social workers and other caregivers to uphold to ensure effective service delivery, safety, and dignity such as respect for autonomy, beneficence, non-maleficence, and justice. The ethics of reciprocity in informal caregiving place a strong emphasis on the value of respect, appreciation, and understanding between carers and care recipients such that when adhered to, both carers and care recipients can enjoy solid, gratifying bonds, have firm self-esteem, self-achievement, and personal growth. Obligations and expectations of care involve understanding that those who once cared for others also need to be appreciated for their effort and support which should be seen as what is morally right and not an obligation that comes with expectations of reciprocity because when these expectations are not met, it leads to emotional strain and ethical dilemmas. Families and caregivers should ensure a balanced approach to care and explore new methods of care that do not rely on expectations and obligations due to the dynamics of change in society. Social workers can contribute to ensuring that caregiving relationships are characterized by genuine love, care, and mutual respect by educating and supporting caregivers to be abreast with the current trend of care plans for older adults, facilitating communication and support between caregivers and care recipients to take charge of their lives, as well as creating awareness in society for people to embrace the shift in mindset by moving away from the notion that caregiving is solely the responsibility of immediate family members and one that requires reciprocity.

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